

NOTES

Terpenoids and Related Compounds - XVIII¹

Triterpenoids of the Leaves of *Rhododendron hodgsoni* Hook

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In connection with our studies on Ericaceae plants, we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the leaves of *Rhododendron hodgsoni* Hook, which is a big tree abundantly distributed in Nepal and Bhutan². The isolation and identification of campanulin, friedelin, α -amyrin, β -amyrin, uvaol, and ursolic acid from the leaves of the plant are reported in the present communication.

Dried and powdered leaves of *R. hodgsoni* were extracted with benzene in a soxhlet apparatus for 10 hrs. The partially crystalline mass obtained after evaporation of benzene was separated into a neutral semicrystalline material and a crystalline acid.

The above crystalline acid on esterification with ethereal diazomethane followed by chromatography afforded a methyl ester, which on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave a solid, m.p. 234–238°. The latter on crystallisation from chloroform and methanol provided pure methyl ursolate acetate, m.p. 240–242°, (α)_D+58.6° (Lit.³ m.p. 244–247°, (α)_D+58°), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen. (TLC⁴: R_f, 0.50).

The semicrystalline neutral component of the plant was chromatographed over a column of activated alumina. Elution with a mixture of pet. ether and benzene (4 : 1) furnished a crystalline solid, which on several crystallisations from a mixture of chloroform and acetone yielded a pure crystalline solid, m.p. 198–201°, (α)_D+64.1°. The melting point and the rotation of the compound closely resembles that of campanulin (TLC⁴: R_f = 0.50). So it was converted into glut-5(10)-en-3 β -ol by refluxing with glacial acetic acid and conc. hydrochloric acid⁵ for 2 hrs. After working up as usual, the crude solid was directly converted into its acetate which on crystallisation from chloroform and acetone furnished pure glut-5-(10)-en-3 β -yl acetate identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen⁵. Thus the compound was characterised as campanulin.

Further elution of the above column with a mixture of pet. ether and benzene (3 : 2) furnished a crystalline solid, which on crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and chloroform yielded friedelin, m.p. 255–258°, (α)_D–33.5°, identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic

1. Part XVII. P. Sengupta and P. B. Das, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in press.
2. J. D. Hooker, "Flora of India", vol. III, p. 464 (1882), L. Reeve and Co., Bank Street, Ashford, Kent, England.
3. P. Boiteau, B. Paisch and A. Rakoto Ratsimamanga, *Les Triterpenoids en physiologie vegetale et animale*, Gauthier-Villars, Paris, 1964, p. 184.
4. For TLC benzene was used as the solvent unless otherwise mentioned.
5. P. Sengupta, S. Ghosh and L. J. Durhum, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 3469.

specimen (TLC⁴ : R_f = 0.40). Elution of the above column with a mixture of benzene and ether (4 : 1) afforded a solid, m.p. 160–175° (showed two spots on TLC) which could not be separated through column chromatography and was directly converted into an acetate mixture, m.p. 165–175° with acetic anhydride and pyridine. The acetate mixture was fractionally crystallised from acetone when the less soluble crop, m.p. 236–240°, (α)_D +76.3° appeared first followed by the more soluble crop, m.p. 218–221°, (α)_D +66.1°. The melting points and rotations of the two compounds correspond to those for β -amyrin acetate and α -amyrin acetate respectively. The identity of the compounds was established by mixed m.p. (undepressed) and TLC with the respective authentic specimens.

Further elution of the above column with a mixture of benzene and ether (2 : 3) furnished a crystalline solid, which on crystallisation from acetone yielded a solid, m.p. 218–220°, (α)_D +66.8° which was identified as uvaol by mixed m.p., TLC and superimposable IR spectra with the authentic specimen.

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